

Harmful Algae News

AN IOC NEWSLETTER ON TOXIC ALGAE AND ALGAL BLOOMS
No. 78 – February 2025 · <https://hab.ioc-unesco.org/>

Intergovernmental
Oceanographic
Commission

Dinoflagellate Blooms and Spinning Fish Coincide with *Sargassum* Inundation, Nitrogen Enrichment and Ocean Warming in the Florida Keys, USA

Harmful algal blooms (HABs) negative impacts on public health, recreation, tourism, fishery, aquaculture, and ecosystems have increased worldwide over the last decades [1]. In subtropical Florida, blooms of cyanobacteria (*Microcystis*, *Synechococcus*, *Lyngbya*), red tides (*Karenia brevis*), brown tides (*Aureoumbra lagunensis*), golden tides (pelagic *Sargassum*) and a variety of benthic macroalgae (*Laurencia*, *Gracilaria*, *Dictyota*, *Wrightiella*, *Cladophora*, *Caulerpa*) have increased in severity in the wake of human population growth over decades. This article provides a brief background of the HABs that have developed in the coastal waters of the Florida Keys (“the Keys”), an island archipelago downstream of the Everglades in southernmost Florida. The coastal waters of the Keys were historically oligotrophic and encompass the majority of the third-longest coral reef in the world, the Florida Reef Tract, which extends 563 kms from the St. Lucie Inlet

on the east coast to the Dry Tortugas National Park west of Key West, FL. The sequence of HABs reached a new level of risk in the Lower Keys in 2023/2024 when unprecedented observations of “spinning fish” and fish kills, most notably the critically endangered small-tooth sawfish (*Pristis pectinata*), were increasingly reported on social media, local U.S. and national news outlets (<https://x.com/NBCNightlyNews/status/1773861243754873069?mx=2>).

Local nutrient pollution from human waste, mainly from leaking septic systems, was first identified as a driver of excessive phytoplankton and macroalgal HABs in the Keys during the 1980s. The resulting eutrophication contributed to low dissolved oxygen and the early stages of seagrass and coral reef die-off [2]. HAB events increased dramatically in the early and mid-1990s when water managers adopted policies to increase freshwater flows from Lake Okeechobee south to Florida Bay and the Keys to re-

Fig. 1. AVHRR reflectance image from March 12 1996 showing a high-turbidity plume from Shark River Slough extending beyond the Lower Florida Keys towards the Dry Tortugas.

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Fig. 2. Dead brain coral (*Pseudodiploria strigosa*) overgrown by the green macroalga *Cladophora vagabunda* in June, 2008 at the Rock Pile, Lower Florida Keys. Photo: Brian E Lapointe.

duce salinity. This policy was controversial as there was no scientific evidence that high salinities were causing either the die-off of seagrasses or hard corals in the Florida Bay and Keys region. The increased runoff was mostly from Shark River Slough in the western Everglades, with smaller flows coming from Taylor Slough into central Florida Bay (Fig. 1). The increased nitrogen-rich ($\sim 1.5 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ Total N) and skewed stoichiometry (N:P $\sim 250:1$) of the Everglades runoff had the unintended consequences of triggering widespread blooms of *Synechococcus*, *Karenia brevis*, and macroalgal overgrowth and die-off of hard corals [3] in southern Florida Bay (Fig. 2). The resulting nutrient-enriched green water flowed downstream from Florida Bay through the tidal channels of the Keys to the ocean side and was followed by a 38% loss of living hard coral cover in the Florida Keys National Marine Sanctuary between 1996 and 2000 [4]. In 2003, the Pew Oceans Commission reported the Florida Keys a U.S. Dead Zone as a direct result of the increasing anthropogenic nutrient loads and resulting oxygen depletion during the 1990s [5]. Large-scale cyanobacterial blooms and die-offs of sponges and hard corals returned to the Florida Bay–Florida Keys region in 2013 following heavy rainfall and increased Everglades runoff following completion of the C-11 Spreader Canal Western Project, which was intended to raise water levels in the eastern Everglades to further increase freshwater flows into central Florida Bay.

The Lower Florida Keys can be directly impacted by the increased flows and turbid plume waters from Shark River Slough and Taylor Slough (Fig. 1), which, combined with local wastewater nutrient pollution, supports widespread blooms of phytoplankton and various red, green and brown macroalgae that overgrow turtle grass (*Thalassia testudinum*) meadows in the shallow channels of the Lower Keys (Fig. 3). The cumulative enrichment of nitrogen and phosphorus at three sites in Pine Channel between Big Pine Key and Upper Harbor Key exceeded established Florida Numeric Nutrient Criteria in 2012/2013, when total dissolved nitrogen (mean TDN= $19.9 \mu\text{M}$;

max of $46.5 \mu\text{M}$) and total dissolved phosphorus (TDP= $0.30 \mu\text{M}$; max of $0.5 \mu\text{M}$) were highest in winter 2013 [6]. The high nutrients supported extensive epiphytic blooms of the red filamentous macroalga *Spyridia filamentosa* on the seagrass *T. testudinum* (40–65 % cover) and were highest at Upper Harbor Key, the site most impacted by runoff from Shark River Slough. The seawater TDN:TDP ratios during the study were also high (mean= $65:1$; max= $90:1$) among the three sites, indicating that the excess nitrogen skewed the high N:P stoichiometry in Pine Channel during the study [6].

Beginning in fall 2023 and continuing into spring 2024, observations of unprecedented “spinning fish” behavior in Pine Channel and the Lower Keys were reported on social media and local news outlets. The first abnormal behavior and mortality of the critically endangered small-tooth sawfish were reported in January 2024 (at Boca Chica beach) and as of July 31, at least 54 died. In addition to the small-tooth sawfish, over 80 species were impacted, including tarpon (*Megalops atlanticus*), snook (*Centropomus undecimalis*), bonefish (*Albula volpes*), goliath grouper (*Epinephelus itajara*), yellowtail snapper (*Ocyurus chrysurus*), flying fish (*Exocoetus volitans*), mutton snapper (*Lutianus analis*) cubera snapper (*Lutjanus cyanopterus*), rainbow parrotfish (*Scarus guacamaia*), southern stingray (*Hypanus americanus*), white mullet (*Mugil curema*), bull shark

Fig. 3. Macroalgae bloom (*Dictyota*, *Wrightiella*, *Laurencia*) overgrowing turtle grass (*Thalassia testudinum*) in Pine Channel, Lower Florida Keys. Photo: Brian E Lapointe.

Fig. 4. MODIS/Aqua ERGB satellite imagery showing ENSO-related discharges from the Everglades in the Lower Florida Keys (red circle) on December 5, 2023, February 3, 2024, and March 7, 2024.

(*Carcharhinus leucas*) and many more [7]. Crustaceans were also affected, including blue crab (*Callinectes sapidus*), Caribbean spiny lobster (*Panulirus argus*), horseshoe crab (*Limulus polyphemus*), spider crab (*Maguimithrax* spp.), and stone crab (*Menippe mercenaria*) [7]. The Florida Department of Environmental Protection conducted water testing for more than 250 chemicals, reporting that most were below detectable limits and none were present at biologically significant concentrations. Dissolved oxygen, salinity, pH and temperature were not suspected to be the cause of the unusual fish behavior or kills. Testing of water, benthic algae, and fish tissue did not detect red tide toxins (brevetoxins produced by *Karenia brevis*), cyanobacterial toxins, or saxitoxins as potential causes [7].

Researchers from Florida Gulf Coast University reported elevated levels of the benthic dinoflagellate *Gambierdiscus* sp. in water of the Lower Keys in early 2024 at concentrations of 1,000 cells·L⁻¹, well above their baseline levels averaging 39 cells·L⁻¹ measured during the previous decade [8]. A more extensive survey of over 150 samples of water, seagrass (*T. testudinum*), and macroalgae (*Dictyota*, *Halimeda*, *Laurencia*) was conducted in spring 2024 to quantify *Gambierdiscus* cell densities and other co-occurring benthic dinoflagellates. A comparison with baseline samples collected previously in the Keys between 2011 and 2023 indicated that *Gambierdiscus* cell densities were, on average, sevenfold higher at sites exhibiting erratic fish behavior in 2024 compared to baseline levels. The researchers suggested that exposure to ciguatoxins produced by the benthic *Gambierdiscus* bloom could partly explain the unusual fish behavior in 2024 [8].

Toxin testing was performed by researchers from the Dauphin Island Sea Lab and University of South Alabama. In vitro assays, targeted liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS), and untargeted LC-high resolution mass spectrometry (LC-HRMS) revealed the bioactivity and presence of a variety of benthic algal toxins in whole water, epiphytic microalgae (20–200 μm) and the tissues of symptomatic fish [9]. Subsequent chemical partitioning and assay-guided fractionation identified ciguatoxins, gambierones, and okadaic acid in water samples. A complex suite of these toxins was also identified in fractionated microalgal extracts. Increased toxin diversity was found at sites in the Lower Keys where fish were most affected, including the detection of portimines in algae and fish, though no known source was identified in preserved samples. Preliminary water-borne exposure in the lab to algal extracts containing toxin mixtures resulted in fish behaviors akin to those observed in the field, prompting further investigations into the components and mechanisms involved [9].

Based on the previous nutrient research in Pine Channel [6], we hypothesized that the bloom of toxic benthic dinoflagellates could be partially linked to unusually high levels of nitrogen enrichment and skewed N:P stoichiometry. South Florida experienced heavy dry-season rainfall in November and December 2023, leading to extreme ENSO-related runoff from both Shark River Slough and Taylor Slough. Remote sensing with MODIS/Aqua imagery showed plumes of discolored water from these discharges impacting the Lower Keys on December 5, 2023, February 3, 2024, and March 7, 2024, spanning the period of unusual fish behavior (Fig. 4; A,B,C). On March 3 and 4, 2024,

local citizen scientists and lead author Lapointe collected water samples for analyses of dissolved nutrients (total dissolved nitrogen, TDN; total dissolved phosphorus, TDP) and dinoflagellate abundance. Water samples were collected from nine sites that included the Newfound Harbor Reef, two sites in Pine Channel, three sites in Bow Channel, and two residential canals, one on Little Torch Key and another on Cudjoe Key. Water temperatures were unusually warm for late winter (25.8–27.7°C) and water samples showed unusually high cell densities (1,000s of cells·L⁻¹) of benthic dinoflagellates. TDN concentrations (mean=29.7 μM, max= 52.1) were much higher (+50%), while TDP concentrations were much lower (-57%; mean=0.13 μM; max=0.23 μM) than the 2012/2013 study [6]. This resulted in extremely skewed TDN:TDP ratios (mean=271:1; max=557) that were fourfold higher than in the 2012/2013 study [6], coinciding with the peak of the 2024 fish spinning event.

Given the high abundance of benthic dinoflagellates in the water column in March 2024, Pine Channel and Upper Harbor Key sites were resampled on April 3rd 2024. This sampling included seawater nutrient analysis and removal of epiphytic dinoflagellates from various macroalgae following the methods of Bomber et al. [10]. Cell densities are reported as cells·gDW⁻¹ based on dry weight (DW) of the macroalgae processed at 65°C for 48 hour in a lab oven. Water temperature remained warm in April (25.3–27.9°C), and TDN, TDP, and TDN:TDP ratios in Pine Channel and Upper Harbor Key were still skewed high (means=24.8 μM, 0.14μM, 224:1). In Pine Channel, dense blooms of *Prorocentrum* were epiphytic on *Cladophora vagabunda* (17 x 10³ cells·gDW⁻¹), *Laurencia intricata* (7.8 x 10³ cells·gDW⁻¹),

and *Digenea simplex* (4.6×10^3 cells·gDW⁻¹), with lower densities of *Ostreopsis* (3×10^3 cells·gDW⁻¹) and *Gambierdiscus* (2.9×10^3 cells·gDW⁻¹) on *Digenea simplex*.

Further sampling was conducted on June 8th 2024 at the Newfound Harbor Reef and Pine Channel sites. TDN, TDP, and TDN:TDP ratios continued to be skewed high at the sites (27.1µM, 0.07µM, 421:1), with very warm temperatures (31.6–32.2°C). Mats of pelagic *Sargassum natans* I, *Sargassum natans* VIII, and *Sargassum fluitans* III were floating at the water surface at Newfound Harbor Reef and were sampled for epiphytic dinoflagellates, along with several benthic macroalgae from Pine Channel. *Prorocentrum lima* (Fig. 5A) was the most abundant dinoflagellate found on all macroalgae at both sites, with maximum densities on *Caulerpa paspaloides* (7.3×10^3 cells·gDW⁻¹), followed by *S. fluitans* III (2.5×10^3 cells·gDW⁻¹), *S. natans* I (2.3×10^3 cells·gDW⁻¹), *Laurencia* spp. (1.7×10^3 cells·gDW⁻¹), *S. natans* VIII (920 cells·gDW⁻¹), and the benthic *S. pteropleuron* (491 cells·gDW⁻¹). *P. hoffmannianum* (Fig. 5B) was most abundant on *Caulerpa paspaloides* (5×10^3 cells·gDW⁻¹) followed by benthic *S. pteropleuron* (2×10^3 cells·gDW⁻¹) and *S. fluitans* III (1.5×10^3 cells·gDW⁻¹). *P. mexicanum* was also abundant on *C.*

paspaloides (2.4×10^3 cells·gDW⁻¹) with lower densities of *Coolia* (318 cells·gDW⁻¹) on *S. fluitans* III.

Densities of toxigenic *Prorocentrum* epiphytic on macroalgae at Newfound Harbor Reef and Pine Channel in June 2024 were similar to those reported for *Gambierdiscus* in the Lower Keys in winter 2024 (8), but notably high compared to previous ciguatera fish poisoning (CFP) studies. Reports of dinoflagellates associated with CFP in the Florida Keys since the 1970s include *Gambierdiscus toxicus*, *Prorocentrum lima*, *P. mexicanum*, *P. concavum*, *P. emarginatum*, *Ostreopsis heptagona*, *O. siamensis*, and *Coolia* spp. [11]. Reported cell densities on pelagic *Sargassum* in the 1980s were lower than those we measured in 2024. For example, between 1983 and 1986 *Prorocentrum lima*, *P. mexicanum*, and *P. concavum* were the most abundant dinoflagellates rafting on *Sargassum natans* in the nearby Straits of Florida with mean densities of 176, 88, and 60 cells·g WW⁻¹, respectively [10]. Considering that the dry weight of *Sargassum* is ~20% of its wet weight, the mean cell density of *P. lima* on *Sargassum fluitans* III and *S. natans* I converted to cells·g WW⁻¹ was almost threefold higher in 2024 than in the 1980s. The high overall dinoflagellate densities of *Prorocentrum* (4.6 to 17×10^3 cells·g DW⁻¹) on benthic *Cladophora*, *Laurencia*, and *Digenea* in Pine Channel in 2024 were similar to densities of *P. lima* on macrophytes in the Fleet Lagoon, UK and other European studies [12].

A review of CFP case studies in the 1950s suggested that these toxigenic events are often associated with disturbed coral reef environments, particularly those impacted by heavy runoff and turbid water [13]. This condition existed in the Lower Keys during winter and spring 2024 when runoff from Shark River Slough and Taylor Slough formed discolored plumes of runoff impacting the Lower Florida Keys (Fig. 4; A,B,C). The salinity of the discolored water at the Newfound Harbor Reef site on the oceanside of the Lower Keys on March 3 2024 was 32.5 psu, confirming the influence of freshwater runoff. The ENSO-related Everglades discharges in winter, combined with local runoff, resulted in extremely high TDN concentrations (mean=29.7 µM, max= 52.1) and TDN:TDP ratios (mean=271:1;

max=557) at the nine sites in the Lower Keys.

Could the combination of exceptionally high TDN, TDN:TDP ratios, warm winter-spring temperatures (24.7–27.9°C) and excessive *Sargassum* inundation (providing a large surface area of substrate for the benthic dinoflagellates) help explain this toxic dinoflagellate bloom and the coincidental spinning fish and mortality event? Batch culture experiments with *Prorocentrum hoffmannianum* run at two temperatures (21 and 27°C) under N-limited (N:P = 0.81) and P-limited (N:P =735:1) conditions showed increased growth and toxin production (okadaic acid) under strong P-limitation at 27°C [14]. These experimental conditions are very similar to those of the Lower Keys in winter and spring 2024 and help explain this unprecedented bloom involving a variety of benthic dinoflagellates that produced multiple lipid-soluble and water-soluble toxins in an unprecedented “toxic cocktail” [9]. This event also followed decades of benthic macroalgal blooms in the Lower Keys that provide more surface area for benthic dinoflagellates, as well as excessive *Sargassum* inundation from the Caribbean region since 2014 [15]. The threefold increase in *Sargassum* biomass in the Atlantic basin [15], combined with a threefold increase in cell density of *Prorocentrum* on *Sargassum*, could have provided a ninefold increase in loading of seed populations of *Prorocentrum* into the Florida Keys. Continued monitoring and research is needed to better understand the “perfect storm” of interacting factors supporting this HAB event and how they could impact the future of fisheries, tourism, and human health in the Florida Keys.

Acknowledgements

The authors gratefully acknowledges the assistance of Gregg and Shaylee Furstenwerth, Scott Hutchinson, Chip Baumberger, and Maggie Vogelsang for assistance with field sampling. Jennifer Cannizzarro (University of South Florida, Optical Oceanography Laboratory) provided the MODIS/Aqua ERGB satellite remote sensing imagery. Greer Babbe and Deanna Webber (Florida Atlantic University-Harbor Branch Oceanographic Institution) assisted

Fig. 5. Scanning electron microscopy micrographs of epiphytic *Prorocentrum lima* (A) and *P. hoffmannianum* (B) from macroalgae collected in the Lower Florida Keys, 2024. Courtesy of Steve Morton and Andrew Shuler.

Fig. 6. Pelagic Sargassum inundation at Bahia Honda State Park, March, 2023. Photo: B E Lapointe.

Fig. 7. Benthic Sargassum pteropleuron in Pine Channel, May, 2024. Photo: B E Lapointe.

Fig. 8. Macroalgal overgrowth (*Halimeda* spp., *Dictyota* sp.) of the Newfound Harbor Reef, May, 2020. Photo: B E Lapointe.

with seawater nutrient processing and analysis. This research would not have been possible without the collaboration with Steve Morton and Andrew Shuler at the HAB Monitoring and Reference Branch, National Centers for

Coastal Ocean Science, NOAA National Ocean Service, 331 Fort Johnson Road, Charleston, SC, USA. Funded by the U.S. National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) Water Resources Program (80NSSC19K1200).

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14883661>